

Cholera Response in Northwest Syria; Community Perspectives and Concerns

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Cite this article: Alkhatib, I.A., Sultanoğlu, E., Salem, M., Saaty, K., Othman, M., Orhun, N.M. Cholera Response in Northwest Syria; Community Perspectives and Concerns. Int J Epidemiol Health Sci 2024;5:e75. Doi: 10.51757/IJEHS.5.2024.715594.

Abstract

Background: In September 2022, the first case of cholera in Northwest Syria was confirmed. The outbreak is compounded by ongoing violence, which complicates efforts to contain it. This study intends to investigate the opinions and concerns of impacted populations in Northwest Syria (NWS) regarding cholera response activities more than a year after the outbreak began.

Methods: The study took a cross-sectional qualitative method. Ten focus group discussions (FGDs) were held in five subdistricts.

Results: The study included 89 participants: health professionals (44) and community leaders (45), 61 (68.5%) men and 28 (31.5%) women, host community members (35) and internally displaced individuals (54). The participants' ages ranged from 20 to 68 years, with a mean of 40.53. Regarding cholera immunization, 75% (66%) reported obtaining it. The study found that participants had a decent awareness of cholera, its causes, dissemination, and symptoms, as well as fair levels of knowledge of prevention measures, but there were gaps in treatment understanding. The findings show a mixed reaction to the epidemic response, with some voicing worries about distrust, poor awareness, and socioeconomic hurdles. Others, on the other hand, remain positive, emphasizing the importance of trusted influencers in raising awareness, with 75% of participants believing in Community Health Workers and 66% in doctors. Rumors of vaccination adverse effects and conspiracy theories were widely published. Financial restrictions limit access to healthcare. Participants noted issues with trash management and availability to clean water.

Conclusion: The study's conclusion provides a detailed picture of the community's cholera response needs, preferences, and problems.

Keywords: Cholera, Outbreak, Response, Vaccine, Syria

Introduction

Cholera is a severe intestinal sickness induced by the consumption of food or water infected with *Vibrio cholerae* O1 and O139 bacteria, which are extremely contagious (1,2). It causes rapid and watery diarrhea; 10% of those infected experience severe symptoms (3,4), which, if not treated immediately, can lead to dehydration and death (1,4,5). In addition, cholera is a major global public health concern, revealing inequities and gaps in socioeconomic development(1). In 2022, cholera outbreaks were documented in 29 countries, particularly in Africa and the Eastern Mediterranean areas (1,6), with the World Health Organization reporting 1.3 million to 4 million cases per year (1,7). Furthermore, cholera primarily affects those living in impoverished areas with little access to clean water and basic sanitation. It flourishes in environments characterized by poor sanitation, overcrowding, violence, and food scarcity (1,4).

Syria has been dealing with a sustained humanitarian catastrophe since the military war began in March 2011, marked by harsh living circumstances and complicated emergencies (8). This battle has resulted in an area in Northwest Syria (NWS), including Idlib governorate and rural Aleppo governorate, that is no longer under government control. As a result, the region's healthcare, water, sanitation, and hygiene systems have reached its capacity (9). Recent findings highlight the severity of the outbreak in this region. As of May 20, 2023, cholera cases have been documented in all 14 governorates of Syria, with Idlib and Aleppo accounting for 35.1% and 29.1%, respectively (10).

The current announcement of a cholera outbreak in Syria (11) began with the first cholera case being confirmed in NWS on September 19th, 2022, and by July 22nd, 2023, the total suspected cases had reached 113,405, with 863 cases confirmed and 24 deaths (12). The rising Cholera outbreak in NWS poses a serious threat to public health, needing prompt and thorough intervention, as well as the implementation of a robust and community-centered response, to prevent the crisis from developing further. The World Health Organization (WHO) and various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) took the lead in responding to this outbreak, with assistance from neighboring Turkey (13). As a result, a cholera taskforce was formed to monitor the outbreak's progress and develop a response plan of action that included coordination, surveillance and reporting, risk communication and community engagement, case management, Infection, Prevention, and Control (IPC), Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH), vaccination, supplies, and research (14).

The situation was exacerbated by two powerful earthquakes in February 2023, which struck Türkiye and NWS in Idlib and Aleppo, causing widespread destruction of residential and public buildings, including hospitals and other infrastructure (15,16). The earthquake has altered living conditions, making them congested and increasing the danger of waterborne infections such as Cholera (11,16).

Despite multiple studies on cholera epidemics, previous research has provided minimal insight into community attitudes toward cholera response, particularly in Syria's most impacted areas that are not under government authority. This study fills a significant research gap by investigating the viewpoints and concerns of impacted communities, diving further into the dynamics of community comment regarding the cholera response more than a year after the outbreak began in NWS. The useful information gathered from this study could inform future treatments and improve the efficiency of cholera response measures in NWS.

Material and methods

Study Design: This study used a cross-sectional qualitative methodology with Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) to gain a thorough understanding of the human elements of the Cholera outbreak in NWS.

Geographic Scope and Site Selection: The study was conducted in five cholera-affected areas: Salqin, Dana, Harim, Atareb, and Afrin in both Aleppo and Idlib governorates in NWS. These five locations were chosen from a total of 35 subdistricts in NWS based on coordination with the Early Warning Alert and Response Network (EWARN) and the cholera response taskforce of the health cluster in NWS, taking into account the most crowded and affected areas with the outbreak. Figure 1 depicts the incidence of probable cholera cases by subdistrict in NWS (17).

Sampling Method, Sample Size and Participant Selection: Individuals with varied levels of knowledge and exposure to the cholera outbreak were identified in coordination with local healthcare officials and community leaders to guarantee a diverse representation of opinions. The study's participants were selected using a purposive sampling strategy. A total of 89 people were involved, including 44 health professionals and 45 community leaders. Participants were divided into two groups: health professionals and community leaders. The health professionals included doctors, nurses, hospital administrative staff, midwives, pharmacists, and lab

technicians. The community leaders included camp managers, teachers, elders in the village, educators, administrative personnel, and female leaders.

Discussion Content and Variables: The main topics of discussion were general understanding about cholera, community attitudes toward cholera response, and accessible AWD/cholera services such as vaccines, awareness campaigns, hygiene kits, and preventive and treatment services. The influence of recent earthquakes on the outbreak and response activities was also examined, as was the efficacy of current response techniques and problems. In addition, the conversations examined community needs and gathered proposals for enhancing cholera prevention and control strategies.

The study looked at the major variables, including:

- Participant demographics include age, gender, residency status, cholera vaccination status, and profession.
- Knowledge and Awareness: Understanding of cholera transmission, symptoms, prevention, preferred sources of information, and habits that contribute to or reduce its spread.
- Assessing the effectiveness and limitations of current cholera response tactics.
- Constraints to cholera response include infrastructure, socio-cultural, and financial constraints.

Ethical Consideration and Informed Consent: Prior to the focus group discussions, informed consent was obtained

from all participants, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their participation, confidentiality, and the purpose of the study. The study was approved by the Health Directorates of Idlib and Aleppo before the initiation of any study procedures.

Moderation And Data Collection: The discussions were conducted by experienced moderators proficient in the local languages, who used a semi-structured interview guide. The handbook addressed issues such as community perceptions of the outbreak, knowledge of cholera, problems encountered, and recommendations for effective intervention techniques. Sessions were audio-recorded to assure data accuracy. The sessions took place from November 19th to December 5th, 2023.

Data Analysis: The MS Excel program was used to discover recurring patterns, major topics, and variances in responses among focus groups. The

qualitative data gathered during the meetings were transcribed, coded, categorized, and analyzed to get valuable insights into the community's reactions to the cholera outbreak.

Results

Ten focus group discussions (FGDs) were held, with 8-10 participants in each. The study included 89 individuals, with 61 (68.5%) men and 28 (31.5%) women. The participants' ages ranged from 20 to 68 years, with a mean age of 40.53.

Knowledge about Cholera Disease

General Knowledge about Cholera Disease: The participants actively participated in conversations, totaling 317 statements about their understanding of cholera. Among these, 41% (130) of the statements came from health providers, while 59% (187) came from community leaders. Among these statements, 42.3% (134) addressed broad knowledge on cholera, including its causes, symptoms, and related information. Fortunately, 62.3% (84) of these statements contained factual and credible information, indicating a commendable awareness across the community. However, 37.6% (50) voiced concern about information scarcity or a lack of understanding about cholera.

Knowledge about the Treatment and Management: The survey revealed a considerable gap in knowledge and comprehension of the procedures and strategies for treating cholera post-infection, with only 28 statements addressing this essential issue. Surprisingly, 43% (12) of these answers emphasized the influential role of single individuals in defining the discourse on cholera treatment, implying a lack of broader engagement among health professionals. In contrast, 57% (16) of the items indicated a limited comprehension or complete lack of awareness about the measures required for effective treatment and care.

Preferred Source of Information: In terms of community choices for cholera-related information sources, participants placed the most faith in health professionals, particularly Community Health Workers (CHWs) and doctors, with substantial percentages of 75% and 66%, respectively. Nurses and pharmacists have a moderate level of trust, with approximately 29% and 18%, respectively. This underscores the importance of health workers as primary informants.

Community and religious leaders show similar levels of trust, at 29% and 21%, respectively. Teachers are

also among the trusted sources, though at a significantly lower rate of 16%. 39% and 24% of people have moderate trust in social media and auditory/visual channels, respectively. On the low end, mothers and e-warn are regarded as less dependable, with single-digit percentages.

Earthquake and it's Impacting the Outbreak

The majority of participants, including two-thirds of health providers and one-third of community leaders, believed that the seismic event had a discernible impact on the cholera outbreak's escalation, citing deteriorating infrastructure and camp overcrowding as key factors. In contrast, a smaller minority claimed that there was no significant increase in the number of cholera cases related with the earthquake.

Most panelists highlighted and acknowledged humanitarian groups' efforts to address cholera issues in the early aftermath of the seismic event. The others presented a different perspective, showing a perceived lack of humanitarian activities.

Attitude Regarding the Outbreak Response

A total of 198 statements provided insight into the community's perceptions towards humanitarian aid and cholera-related services. Notably, many participants, particularly community influencers, expressed worry about widespread skepticism, a lack of information, and considerable socioeconomic constraints influencing the cholera outbreak response. Previous unpleasant experiences with health care have instilled a widespread sense of distrust, prompting people to take issues into their own hands. Conversely, a sizable proportion of interviewees had a more hopeful outlook. They emphasized trustworthy characters like as teachers and community influencers who use their knowledge to raise awareness, giving optimism for better involvement and response to the cholera outbreak.

A health professional stated:

“Raising awareness among family members and the surrounding community, as well as distributing cholera leaflets to pharmacies and private clinics. My responsibility is to educate patients about the severity of the condition, the mechanisms of infection, and how to prevent it. I was really worried when I came in contact with a patient who had the same symptoms.”

Despite acknowledging the provision of cholera care, participants reach a remarkable consensus: they believe these services are deficient. This overriding impression highlights a significant discrepancy

between community expectations and the perceived effectiveness of the humanitarian response.

Approximately one-third of participants reported engaging in good and healthy practices either individually or collectively within the community. However, a bigger segment reported a lack of knowledge about basic health behaviors. Notably, many of these harmful practices were linked to obstacles such as poor hygienic facilities and clean drinking water in camps or communities, as well as resident financial issues.

The majority of interviewees reported that the community's priorities frequently shift toward basic needs rather than seeking information regarding the severity of the cholera outbreak. Many comments underline the importance of giving food baskets or hygiene kits in addition to services, highlighting a significant gap in the community's awareness of the urgency of the cholera crisis. Financial and transportation issues appear as important impediments, enabling some community members to choose to face the disease without obtaining help from health services.

In general, humanitarian actors have observed a lack of coordination and the absence of a unified governance authority, which has resulted in delays in declaring outbreaks, redundant efforts, misinformation, and community hesitation.

Cholera Response Services

Cholera Awareness Interventions: The majority of participants responded that they were aware of the awareness efforts that had taken place and that more awareness and orientation activities were required. The most significant shared interest of community leaders and health practitioners has been the participation and empowerment of community influencers to lead awareness campaigns.

Some interviewees mentioned a lack of awareness initiatives in certain areas, particularly the Salqin subdistrict, as well as a lack of trust in humanitarian personnel.

Cholera Response on The Health Center Level: Surprisingly, a large majority of participants expressed pleasure and thankfulness for the available health centers. The sentiment expressed represented a good acknowledgement of the efforts made to improve healthcare facilities. In contrast, a smaller but significant minority, 32% (37), expressed a different viewpoint and drew attention to perceived shortcomings in the capability of health facilities, notably the problems created by the cholera outbreak.

Figure 1. Map of prevalence of suspected cholera cases per subdistricts in NWS (17)

Table 1. Summary of the Study Methodology

Aspect	Details
Study Design	Cross-sectional qualitative approach utilizing Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)
Geographic Scope and Site Selection	Five cholera-affected locations: Salqin, Dana, Harim, Atareb, and Afrin in Aleppo and Idlib governorates, NWS. Selected from 35 subdistricts based on EWARN and health cluster coordination. Figure 1: Map of prevalence.
Sampling Method	Purposive sampling method.
Sample Size	Total of 89 participants: 44 health professionals and 45 community leaders.
Participant Selection	Health professionals: doctors, nurses, hospital staff, midwives, pharmacists, lab technicians. Community leaders: camp managers, teachers, elders, educators, administrative employees, women leaders.
Discussion Content	General knowledge about cholera, community attitudes, available AWD/cholera services, impact of earthquakes, effectiveness of response strategies, challenges, and community needs.
Variables	Participant Demographics: Age, gender, residency status, cholera vaccination status, profession. Knowledge and Awareness: Levels of knowledge, awareness, and practices. Response Strategies: Effectiveness and challenges. Barriers: Infrastructure, socio-cultural, and financial barriers.
Informed Consent	Obtained prior to FGDs, emphasizing voluntary participation, confidentiality, and study purpose.
Ethical Approval	Ethical approval was obtained from Health Directorates of Idlib and Aleppo.
Moderation and Data Collection	Experienced moderators facilitated discussions using a semi-structured guide. Sessions were audio-recorded. Dates: November 19 to December 5, 2023.
Data Analysis	Content analysis using MS Excel to identify patterns, themes, and variations. Data were transcribed, coded, and analyzed for insights.

Table 2. Number of participants in focus group discussions by cadre

	Focus Groups Discussions Participants (N=89)	
	Health Professional n =44	Community Leaders n=45
Residency Status		
Host Communities	18	17
Internally displaced people (IDP)	26	28
Sex		
Male	32	29
Female	12	16

Figure 2. The community's preferences for cholera-related information sources

Cholera Response on The Humanitarian Response Level: A total of 276 comments were examined to evaluate humanitarian relief actions in response to the cholera disease, which included services such as awareness and orientation exercises, household visits, vaccine campaigns, cholera kits, and IEC dissemination. Impressively, a significant 71% (197) expressed thanks and gratitude for the humanitarian assistance provided by numerous groups, identifying specific activities and their impact. A significant 29% (79) of respondents disagreed.

Cholera Kits and Supplies: About 64% of participants are pleased with the quality and number of provided cholera kits, but 36% are concerned about their size and advise larger quantities or more frequent distributions. Some argue that, in addition to kit distribution, more critical services are required. Increased knowledge of correct kit use is promoted, with a focus on community education. There is a request to enhance supply, particularly clean water and hygiene products.

Cholera and Vaccination: Seventy-five percent (66 individuals) reported receiving the cholera vaccine, whereas twenty-five percent (23 participants) did not. Some interviewees highlighted the presence of poor conditions for vaccination programs. Another notable observation was a lack of understanding regarding vaccine campaigns, including their availability, nature, and source. There have also been some comments that include falsehoods concerning the cholera vaccination, such as "the vaccine causes impotence." (A community leader stated).

Furthermore, several participants mentioned issues with trash disposal procedures and a perceived lack of capacity, indicating a varied perspective on the operational aspects of vaccine campaigns in the community.

The dataset contains 36 statements that consistently demonstrate the frequency of misperception among afflicted persons. This misunderstanding exacerbated unwillingness to adopt the cholera vaccine. Rumors included fears about the vaccine's negative effects, skepticism about its efficiency, and baseless conspiracy theories regarding its origin or composition.

A Camp Manager stated:

"We are in a zone of war, and during such times, vaccine manufacturers frequently conduct tests. I refuse to be a testing ground or to take the vaccine so that it is not tested on me."

Barriers Against Cholera Response

Infrastructure Barriers: The study of infrastructural hurdles found that 93% of statements highlighted major gaps that impeded access to cholera-related services due to transit challenges, budgetary limits, and health-care facility issues. Most participants expressed concern about contaminated water sources and challenges in adopting healthy practices. Some cited community initiatives and positive attitudes toward sewage systems, but the majority stressed the obstacles caused by damaged infrastructure, overcrowded camps, and limited access to clean water. However, some participants gave a different perspective and put light on community efforts and initiatives by specific organizations working to address this issue.

Significant concerns were raised concerning a lack of necessary resources such as staff, medicine, health facility kits, and infrastructure materials, which prevented patients from receiving effective health care. Waste disposal challenges and perceived inadequate capacity were also highlighted.

Socio-Cultural Barriers: Within the large amount of information gathered from the ten FGDs, only 20 remarks explicitly mentioned socio-cultural hurdles in the context of the cholera outbreak response. This seemingly limited representation can be read in two ways: either socio-cultural factors have little influence on the answer, or these obstacles are underreported or poorly understood.

Financial Barriers: The overwhelming majority, 92% of the responses collected, emphasized that transportation and financial constraints are the primary barriers causing impacted individuals to shun health facilities. Most participants emphasized significant financial and transportation hurdles during the cholera outbreak, with worries about delayed access to health services due to inadequate transportation infrastructures. These obstacles impede timely access to healthcare as well as the availability of clean water and vital drugs, both of which are critical for cholera treatment.

Community Needs

The majority of interviewees underlined the urgency of responding to the cholera outbreak. They emphasized the importance of comprehensive sanitation and sewage system improvements, as well as collaborative waste management and awareness programs. Addressing logistical hurdles to getting health care, such as transportation and clinic hours, was regarded as critical. Cholera outreach initiatives were used to target high-risk individuals, as well as collaborate with local community leaders and

influencers. Raising awareness about all facets of the cholera pandemic became a top focus. Additionally, addressing transportation and financial barriers to access to health care, conducting periodic vaccination campaigns, and providing extra supplies such as soaps, clean water, and hygiene kits were emphasized as critical interventions.

Discussion

The findings of this qualitative study provide significant insights into the perceptions of impacted communities in NWS, as well as some key themes that are important in evaluating the efficacy and problems of the present cholera response. The study revealed a significant degree of participation and awareness among participants, with the majority displaying accurate knowledge about cholera, its sources, dissemination, and symptoms, as well as fair knowledge of cholera preventative strategies. However, there were significant knowledge gaps about cholera treatment and care. Participants recognized the efforts made to raise cholera awareness, but underlined the need for more focused and inclusive programs. Health professionals, particularly CHWs and doctors, were the most reliable providers of cholera information. However, moderate trust in other sources, such as social media and community leaders, suggests opportunities to improve communication strategies.

The findings identify substantial problems and potential for development. Many participants showed widespread suspicion and skepticism about humanitarian aid and cholera-related services. While they acknowledge the provision of cholera services, participants agree that these services are deemed insufficient, demonstrating a substantial gap between offered services and community expectations. A large proportion of interviewees indicated a lack of commitment to good health practices, which was exacerbated by inadequate hygienic facilities, restricted access to clean water in camps, and financial issues among inhabitants. Despite the fact that 75% of participants reported receiving the cholera vaccine, some highlighted unpleasant conditions during vaccination campaigns, as well as a substantial lack of understanding regarding the vaccinations' availability and use. Misinformation generated skepticism, with concerns about side effects, doubts about efficacy, and conspiracy theories revealing deep-seated fears in the community.

The study revealed fundamental impediments to a successful cholera response, namely infrastructure and budgetary constraints. There are significant transportation gaps, tainted water, and damaged

infrastructure. Sociocultural hurdles were identified less frequently, which could indicate underreporting. Resource shortages, such as staff, medicine, and infrastructural materials, hampered access to health services, as did issues with waste disposal procedures. Another key challenge in NWS is the lack of a unified governing body, which has resulted in a tendency to avoid officially declaring cholera outbreaks, instead labeling them as Acute Watery Diarrhea (AWD).

The study's findings are consistent with previous research from Lebanon examining Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices (KAP) (18), which discovered high levels of cholera awareness among afflicted individuals. This closeness in results implies that effective cholera education and awareness initiatives may be implemented even under difficult circumstances. Furthermore, the study's findings are consistent with prior research, which has recognized the involvement of media, community influencers, and health professionals as a significant component in the success of disseminating accurate and timely messaging (18-19). Inadequate information and awareness, combined with ineffective disease control strategies, can result in cholera transmission (20). Similar findings regarding trust in health professionals and the need for effective public education can be found in studies from the Democratic Republic of Congo (21), which revealed that healthcare providers appreciated the cholera response but emphasized the importance of long-term support for fundamental public health measures. These studies underline the importance of healthcare providers in increasing community knowledge and resolving treatment-related concerns. The study's participants agreed that the source of drinking water has been linked to a variety of infectious disorders, citing past research that suggests a link between groundwater and enteric infections (18,22).

In terms of cholera vaccine uptake, the findings are consistent with those from a previous qualitative study conducted in Mozambique, which demonstrated hesitation toward oral cholera vaccination(23). The study revealed that community engagement is an important component of trust-building measures targeted at fighting the cholera pandemic. This is consistent with a similar statement made by a research conducted in Zambia(24), which underlined the need of giving information about the efficacy of the cholera vaccination and potential side effects. This method tries to increase vaccine uptake while countering any conspiratorial notions about the vaccine.

The study findings are also consistent with research conducted in Zanzibar (25) which highlighted the importance of trust in health systems, efficient

implementation of vaccine campaigns, free vaccinations, and other operational difficulties as key factors influencing cholera vaccine acceptance.

In terms of barriers to proper outbreak control, a study conducted in the Democratic Republic of Congo (21) revealed comparable constraints, emphasizing the impact of financial constraints, insufficient staff training, and deficiencies in referral pathways on cholera response and treatment-seeking behavior. Another study on the issues of cholera prevention and control in the Eastern Mediterranean region found comparable constraints (26). Political instability, conflict, insecurity, mass gatherings, and densely populated environments, particularly in areas with inadequate WASH programs within camps housing internally displaced people, increase susceptibility to cholera outbreaks and other infectious diseases(26,27). The lack of a cohesive governing body resulted in the withholding of laboratory test results and intentional underreporting of cases, resulting in insufficient control measures (26). As a result, the World Health Organization has prioritized the implementation of a comprehensive and integrated cholera prevention and control plan, spanning both the health and WASH sectors, to ensure effective cholera outbreak management (1).

In contrast, KAP research on cholera in countries such as Bangladesh(28) and Yemen(29) consistently show a lack of awareness of cholera and its prevention. This is in contrast to the relatively high levels of awareness found in the study. Furthermore, studies from the Democratic Republic of the Congo (30) and South Africa (31) revealed high levels of awareness of cholera therapy, most likely as a result of prior outbreaks in those countries. This contrasts with the study's finding that there is a significant lack of understanding about cholera treatment and management. It is clear that there is insufficient involvement from health experts in educating the population about appropriate treatment regimens.

This study gives a complete overview of community perceptions on the cholera response in NWS, emphasizing affected populations' viewpoints rather than clinical or logistical factors. The inclusion of diverse participant groups, such as male and female participants, host community members, internally displaced persons (IDPs), health professionals, and community leaders, ensures a diverse range of perspectives and a more comprehensive understanding of the cholera response. This diversity adds depth to the findings and enables for a more nuanced view of the varied issues that different sectors of the population face.

The study's limitations stemmed mostly from the demanding backdrop of conflict zones. The geographical coverage was limited to NWS, hence

the findings may not be applicable to other locations. The limited sample size, albeit well representative, may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Furthermore, the use of qualitative data introduces subjectivity, despite efforts to ensure accurate representation via purposive sampling and content analysis. Key Informant Interviews (KIIs) combined with Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) might have provided deeper insights and a more thorough grasp of the concerns.

Conclusion

The findings show that the population has a nuanced understanding of cholera, with high awareness of the disease but major gaps in treatment knowledge, underlining the need for increased health professional participation. Despite certain trust concerns, there is enthusiasm in community-led initiatives, demonstrating the value of collaborative efforts. Distrust, a lack of awareness, and socioeconomic restrictions continue as a result of poor prior experiences. Trusted community figures are essential for raising awareness and creating trust. Participants have differing perspectives on health practices: while some recognize healthy habits, many are unaware due to infrastructure and budgetary constraints. Barriers to getting aid highlight the importance of coordinated actions to address these challenges and prevent disinformation.

Many participants attribute the spread of the cholera outbreak to the earthquake, however some disagree. Concerns regarding the effectiveness of the post-earthquake response remain, with infrastructure deterioration and camp overpopulation cited as important contributors.

Gratitude is expressed for health centers, however service shortages are identified. Misinformation has a substantial impact on vaccine hesitancy, emphasizing the necessity for correct information dissemination. While the majority of people enjoy cholera kits, reservations regarding their appropriateness highlight the need for improved support and increased awareness of safe usage.

Infrastructure impediments have a huge impact on the outbreak, including large gaps in sewage systems, waste management, and healthcare access. Financial constraints further limit access to essential services.

A comprehensive response is urgently required, with a focus on waste management, awareness campaigns, and sewage system monitoring. Addressing logistical constraints, focusing on high-risk populations, and partnering with local leaders are critical for effective intervention.

Acknowledgments

We express our heartfelt gratitude to the AFAQ Humanitarian Relief Organization for their tremendous financial support, which made this study possible. We are really grateful to the participants for their cooperation and willingness to take part in this research. The research assistants deserve special mention for their significant efforts to organizing Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and data collection. Furthermore, we would like to thank the health directorates for allowing us to perform this study.

Conflicts of interest

There are no competing interests.

Informed Consent Statement

Prior to the start of the study, all participants gave their informed consent and willingly participated in the Focus Group Discussions (FGD).

Funding

This study was supported by the AFAQ humanitarian relief organization.

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